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Predicting the Likelihood of Wolf Sightings in Upper Austria

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Predicting the Likelihood of Wolf Sightings in Upper Austria project. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the Horizon Europe DMP template.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
KB	Kilobyte

MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the Horizon Europe DMP template. Martin Stöckl will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

The project reuses existing data originally collected and published by the state of Upper Austria. This dataset consists of structured tabular data in HTML format, which is later extracted and converted into CSV files during the data preparation phase. No alternative dataset of comparable scope and relevance for Upper Austria was available.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Land Oberösterreich - Wolfsmanagement in Oberösterreich	https://www.land-oberoesterreich.gv.at/517622.htm	Reuse permitted, requires Attribution	no

The purpose of the reused dataset is to produce derivative datasets that are suitable for model training. The purpose of the generated data is to train and evaluate a machine learning model capable of predicting the likelihood of future wolf sightings at different locations and times.

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	wolf_sighting_events.csv	Plain text	CSV	60 - 100 KB	no
P2	wolf_sightings_processed.csv	Plain text	CSV	70 - 100 KB	no
P3	wolf_sightings_model.pkl	Serialized binary	PKL	2 - 4 MB	no
P4	wolf_sightings_kmeans.pkl	Serialized binary	PKL	1 - 5 KB	no
P5	wolf_sightings_raw.csv	Plain text	CSV	30 - 50 KB	no

All produced data is structured in CSV format for tabular datasets and in PKL (Pickle) format for serialized machine learning models. In addition, the project generates visual artifacts for evaluating the

model, which are saved in PNG format. The total expected size of all generated and reused datasets is small, with no file exceeding 5MB. The estimated total size of produced data is less than 10MB.

The provenance of the reused data is clearly traceable to the Upper Austrian government’s public datasets. The generated data originates from the structured transformation, enrichment, and extension of this input during the experiment, following the steps that are rigorously documented in the Provided Jupyter Notebooks.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The HTML data will be processed inside a Jupyter Notebook using Python. This generates a CSV file containing the data from the tables of the HTML page. This data serves as the foundation for all further data generated as part of this project.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

The data is expected to primarily be useful to the general public, interested in finding out the likelihood of encountering wolves. It may prove useful to holders of livestock. It may also be useful to researchers working in ecology, environmental management, and regional planning fields.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All datasets generated during the project are assigned individual persistent identifiers through TU Wien DBRepo. The generated datasets are annotated with a description, which details the purpose and contents of the respective dataset. Evaluation outputs and trained models are uploaded to the TU Wien Research Database repository, which is also assigned a persistent identifier. We make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation. Consistent naming conventions are used across all repositories. Version control is automated.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to all of our created datasets. Since we have no control over the related dataset hosted by the state of Upper Austria, we cannot guarantee it’s long term available

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-02-28	TU Wien DBRepo	DOI: 10.82556/8jpm-	CC-BY-4.0

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
					3v20	
P2	Open		2025-02-28	TU Wien DBRepo	DOI: 10.82556/t9bj-x612	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open		2025-02-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: 10.70124/j49xf-khk42	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open		2025-02-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI: 10.70124/j49xf-khk42	CC-BY-4.0
P5	Open		2025-02-28	TU Wien DBRepo	DOI: 10.82556/7fyc-at60	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

To perform predictions using the trained model, an environment for running Jupyter Notebooks is required. The required code can be downloaded from the associated Github repository.

No data is embargoed except for the DMP itself, which is temporarily embargoed until the exercise deadline, as per course instructions. After the embargo, the DMP will also be publicly available on Zenodo. Access to the datasets does not require authentication. All files are accessible via free, open, standardized protocols, with no restrictions or access committees needed.

Software dependencies required for accessing and processing the data (e.g., Python libraries listed in requirements.txt) are documented and made available in the source code repository.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We will make our data interoperable by using widely accepted, non-proprietary formats. Tabular data is provided in CSV format, Machine learning models are serialized in PKL (Pickle) format, and visual outputs are saved in standard PNG format. Interoperability is ensured by adhering to common data modeling practices. Categorical features are clearly defined, and numerical features use consistent units and scales. Where domain-specific standards were lacking, best practices for machine learning data interoperability were followed, including feature documentation via README files, extensive descriptions accompanying Jupyter code cells, and explicit field names in the CSV files.

2.4. Increase data re-use

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns. All developed code is published under the MIT License. Data quality was assured through manual validation of geocoding results, visual inspection of cluster assignments, and evaluation of the trained models via standard performance metrics such as ROC-AUC and precision-recall curves.

3. Other research outputs

The primary machine learning output is a trained Random Forest Classifier capable of predicting wolf sighting probabilities based on spatial and temporal features. The model is serialized and saved in PKL format. It has been uploaded to TUWRD with a DOI for permanent referencing. Jupyter Notebooks documenting the preprocessing (data cleaning, feature engineering) and model training processes have been developed and are available inside the GitHub repository. Comprehensive code annotations were added to make workflows reproducible.

A prototype application for interactive prediction is included in the training notebook, allowing users to select a location and time and receive predicted sighting probabilities. This interface demonstrates practical application of the model and enhances transparency.

Each of these research outputs is managed according to the same FAIR principles as the datasets. Metadata, licensing information (MIT License for code, CC-BY 4.0 for outputs), and provenance documentation are consistently applied across all outputs. All code and documentation have been made available on GitHub, with an assigned DOI through Zenodo for citation.

4. Allocation of resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR. No paid cloud storage or proprietary tools were necessary. The project relies exclusively on Zenodo, and institutional infrastructure provided by TU Wien, including DBRepo and TUWRD. The time investment mainly covered data preprocessing, documentation creation and repository uploads. These activities were completed individually as part of course requirements, with no need for external funding.

Long-term preservation is ensured by the policies of TU Wien repositories, which guarantee data availability for at least 10 years. Future curation efforts, if necessary, will depend on institutional archival policies and will not incur additional costs at project level.

5. Data security

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Martin Stöckl (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will not be stored on TU Wien servers.

P2 (wolf_sightings_processed.csv), P1 (wolf_sighting_events.csv) will be stored on TUWien DBRepo.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. Since all processed data is publicly available from government sources and does not contain personal information, there is no sensitive data to protect.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
R1	no access	no access	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien DBRepo	10 years
P2	TU Wien DBRepo	10 years
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P4	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P5	TU Wien DBRepo	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

6.1. Personal data

The project does not contain personal data. There are no ethical or legal concerns related to data sharing for this project.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The project author, Martin Stöckl, has access control rights over all datasets and artifacts that are published as part of this project. The reused data is publicly available from a governmental website without any usage restrictions, except the requirement for attribution, which was given on all derived datasets.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.